

A Study on Awareness and Satisfaction towards Employee Welfare Measures

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ABSTRACT

The employees are considered as major resources of all organisations including service as well as manufacturing industries. So in the present day of business world, the companies are giving more benefits to their employees and maintaining good standard measures to make them satisfy in the organisation. The present study is on the above subject which studies the welfare measures. Therefore the reason of the study is to find out how welfare measure are provided by the private organisation and how the employees are satisfied with the company accommodation given to the employees which plays a very important role in the employee satisfaction and their life in the organization. The study found that the employee welfare measures are highly satisfactory in their concern which was done through perfect analysis & interpretation. This study would be helpful for the company and also to improve some welfare and safety activities inside the company.

Keywords-- Welfare Measures, Employees, Organisation, Employees Satisfaction

utilized is them to play out their work in solid and serene environment and to profit of offices which enhance their wellbeing and bring high assurance." As per the panels on Employee Welfare (1969), "Representative welfare incorporates such administrations, Facilities and conveniences as sufficient bottle, rest and diversion offices, sterile and therapeutic offices, game plans for movement to in their own place and have a different administrations, courtesies, offices involves standardized savings level will they add to enhance the condition under which specialists are utilized."

As per the definitions of employee welfare, we can describe it by few points as given below.

- To create best life and improve the wellness to the employee.
- To make the workers strong, healthy and effective.
- To enhance scholarly, social and material states of living of the worker and to diminish them from mechanical worries.

I. INTRODUCTION

The employees are considered as major resources of all organisations including service as well as manufacturing industries. So in the present day of business world, the companies are giving more benefits to their employees and maintaining good standard measures to make them satisfy in the organisation. Thus by the concept of welfare measures to employees the organisation can make their employees satisfied up to the mark. There can't be a solitary meaning of worker welfare at the same time as it is an active idea in which new-fangled welfare measures are additional to the existing ones at the side of social changes. The advanced idea of employee welfare engross each one of those put into effect of the businesses which are coordinated towards furnishing the workers with specific offices and administrations not withstanding wages or pay rates. A welfare administration is just support factors and not sparks, yet they are fundamental for the soundness of the organisation since they bear a nearby organisation with the productivities of the representative power.

As per ILO report, "Employee' welfare ought to be comprehended as including such administrations, civilities and offices which must be built up in or in the prompt area of endeavours to empower the people

II. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The employees are considered as major resources of all organisations including service as well as manufacturing industries. So in the present day of business world, the companies are giving more benefits to their employees and maintaining good standard measures to make them satisfy in the organisation. The present study is on the above subject which studies the welfare measures of Nithya Packing Limited present at Villianur of Pondicherry U.T. There are more number of man power is available in the company. The specialty of the company is the manpower cannot be substituted with any other professional except engineering. The role of manpower in the company is very critical. Recently manpower turnover is the biggest issue in the industry. This causes the productivity and performance of the company.

The company works in its own way. When a new employee is appointed by the company it takes months of stress and strain to train the staff and make him suitable and adaptable to the purpose and operation of the company. But the sad part is the company appointing the employees temporary. The employees are aware that even though the company providing the good welfare measure still it not satisfied because of the standard of job. Even

though the company provide lots of welfare measure in some situation it is not worked out properly because of employee conflicts. In that situation the company wants to replace the employee to fill the vacant place. In this time company want train the employee again to replace the vacant area.

Therefore the reason of the study is to find out how welfare measure are provided by the company and how the employees are satisfied with the company accommodation given to the employees which plays a very important role in the employee satisfaction and their life in the organization.

III. NEED FOR THE STUDY

In the present globalised era, the cost of living and other situational factors induce employees and the employers to go for the better benefits for the employees in the organization. Employers too have discovered that incidental advantages display alluring zones of transaction when substantial wage and compensation increments are not doable. Rapid industrialization, progressively substantial urbanization and the development of a free enterprise economy have made it troublesome for most workers to ensure themselves against the unfriendly effect of these improvements. Since it was specialists who are in charge of creation, it was held that businesses ought to acknowledge duty regarding addressing a portion of the necessities of their workers. Accordingly, a few advantages and-administrations programs were received by bosses.

The developing volume of work enactment, especially standardized savings enactment, made it basic for managers to share similarly with their representatives the cost of maturity, survivor and incapacity benefits. The examiner has been taken up keeping in mind the end goal to distinguish how the **Nithiya Packaging Limited** is putting forth different representative advantages. The investigation is gone for seeing every one of the parts of representative advantages projects and plans that are worried about pulling in, overseeing, rousing and creating workers for the advantage of the association.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The primary objective of the present research is to analyses the employee's awareness and satisfaction towards welfare measures in Nithiya Packaging Ltd., Pondicherry.

The secondary objectives includes,

- To find out the awareness among the employees about the employee welfare measures.
- To identify satisfaction level for the employees towards health and safety measures provide by the company.
- To identify the impact of respondents profile on overall satisfaction towards welfare measures of the company.

- To provide suggestions to improve industrial relations through enhanced employee welfare measures.

Hypothesis for the Study

H0: There is no significant relationship between overall satisfaction and Medical faculties, canteen facilities, good working environment and toilet facility.

V. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Options expressed by the employees in the questionnaire may not be genuine or what they actually feel and there is ever chance of bias coming into play.
- The information collected from the employees is limited because of their busy schedule.
- As the organization structure is very wider it is difficult for me to understand the employee activities in the organization.

VI. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Survey of writing is an imperative perspective in any exploration ponders as it gives a profound comprehension of the examination issue and a very clear introduction to the scientists. Examiners get a reasonable feeling of centre by discovering what has just been done and the holes in the exploration considers. It additionally helps in moulding and controlling the examination a productive way by offering profound bits of knowledge and alternate points of view on the exploration theme.

Selvaraj (1995) has made an investigation with the goal of lessening the rate of mishaps and to enhanced mechanical relations. The investigation has discovered that the working conditions positively impact inspiration and assurance of the representative and will build their sense of duty regarding work. In connection to the same above subject, Rban Singh (2001) also made an investigation to manage workplace inside the processing plant. The examination made infers that the hardware inside the processing plant ought to be kept flawlessly cleaned and fenced legitimately which would maintain a strategic distance from mishap.

According to the Report of National Commission on Employee (2002) Government of India, made suggestions in the territory of Employee welfare measures which incorporate government managed savings, broadening the use of the Provident Fund, tip and joblessness protection and so on. N. K. Jetli (2004) pointed out that employee changes in India, with regards to globalization, are quite wanted, yet in addition dreaded and misjudged. The issue has been an unstable one as far back as the advancement time started in the mid-1990. Worker changes are an extremely touchy subject in the Indian setting, given the ground substances of destitution, ignorance, diseases, hardship, abuse, and per capita salary. Worker advertises changes include institutional advancement. Rushed endeavours to change the lawful

structure without making Institutions fitting for another administrative administration will make anarchic conditions in the Employee advertise. A program of Employee approach change must be figured with these contemplations in see. This snare looks at the entire range of Employee issues with regards to financial progression in progress in India.

In India, 2005 Employee Benefits Report, by government of India has pointed out that employee benefits have been at the cutting edge of political level headed discussions and representative arrangements for a long while. The absence of data identifying with representative advantages has left Rhode Island businesses making numerous inquiries in regard to where they remain in examination with different bosses in the state.

Subburao. Y. V (2006) conducted an empirical investigation to examine the welfare measures of employees and examination in welfare plan of working representatives. The goal of the investigation was to prescribe and demonstrates the different workers feeling to the organization towards welfare plans. The study results revealed that the employees are satisfied with the existing welfare measures by the company. There is a positive relationship between overall satisfaction and welfare measures in the organisation.

Bhavani and Tamil Selvan (2011) studied about employees welfare measures, and pointed out that India has changed its financial approaches in 1991, it has emphatically reacted and now India is considered as one of the dynamic developing countries. As of late the World Bank figures that by 2020, India could turn into the fourth biggest economy on the planet. The changed financial strategies give gigantic chance to the outside organizations to begin business in India. This prompts expanded level of rivalry and put weight on local organizations human asset capacities. To survive and thrive, in this hardest aggressive condition, they need to get ready and build up their representatives to contend with abroad associations in abilities, proficiency and adequacy. The satisfactory welfare measures will upgrade the sound modern relations in the associations.

M.Rama Satyanarayana and R.Jayaprakash Reddy (2012) studied the consideration is embraced by the creators to know the fulfilment levels of workers about representative welfare measures in KCP constrained. The consequences of the examination uncover that greater part of the workers are happy with all the welfare measures gave by the association. The general fulfilment levels of representatives about welfare measures in the association cover under investigation are agreeable. In any case, a couple are not happy with welfare measures gave by the association. It is recommended that the current welfare measures might be enhanced further. Such welfare measures enhance the representatives' way of life and their fulfilment levels.

Minakshi Garg and Pardeep Jain (2013) pointed out the Industrial advance relies upon fulfilled

representative power and in this association the significance of worker welfare measures was acknowledged long back. Worker welfare idea is essentially in light of human esteems, where every native has a privilege to work in an amiable situation without any perils to his wellbeing on sensible wages and different terms and states of business. The days are over when representative was thought to be an item. At the point when a specialist joins industry he needs to work in a whole weird air, making issues of change. Having a fulfilled workforce is particularly fundamental for smooth working of each association. So this investigation is directed to know whether the specialists are happy with the welfare offices gave by material ventures in Punjab. This examination has additionally endeavoured to contemplate connection between the sex of the respondents and mindfulness on welfare measures.

VII. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used the descriptive design for this minor research to describe the facts about the welfare measures of the company. The study used both primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected through structured questionnaire and secondary data were collected from journal articles, company records and website.

For the gathering of samples from the personnel branch, from the list of 400 employees by name, department, in addition to nature of duty have been collected as well as from this list 100 samples have been selected randomly for the present study. The collected data have been analyzed with the help of tools like simple percentage method as well as Multiple regression analysis.

Regression analysis is also implemented to confirm the relationship between the three variables. A linear regression is analyzed in the study. Multiple regression analyses are conducted to examine the relationship between OS with *MF*, *CF*, *WE* and *TF*. Multiple regression analyses are conducted to observe the relationship among overall satisfaction (OS) with *MF*, *CF*, *WE* and *TF*. Where, *MF*: Medical Facility, *CF*: Canteen Facility, *WE*: good work environment, *TF*: Toilet Facilities, and B_0, B_1, B_2, B_3 and B_4 are constants.

VIII. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This section tries to show the data analysis part. It has classified into three sections. First section describes about demographic profile of the respondents, second section deals with the awareness and satisfaction level of employees about the welfare measures of the company and third section deals with the hypotheses testing.

Part-I

The 17 % of the respondent is in the age group of above 25-30, 36 % respondent is in the age group of

above 41-50, 40 % of the respondent is the age group of 31-40 and remaining 7 % of the respondents are in the age group of 21-30. Therefore, dominant part of the respondent is in the age gathering of 31 or more. The respondents of 80 % are male and 20 % of the respondents are female. It is inferred that dominant of the respondents are male. When comes to the income level most of the respondents fall under the wage between Rs.10000 – 15,000. Very few case, minimal number of respondent falls under the class of above Rs.25000. The greater part of respondents 10000-15000 was 34%. From the analysis, it concludes that above 32% of respondents

have completed diploma, and 09 % had engineering, so the company give first preference to technical person at the time of recruiting because it is manufacturing company. Remaining falls under other categories. The marital status showed that out of 100 respondents 75% are married and remaining of them are 25% unmarried.

Part-II

This section describes about various welfare measures awareness and satisfaction of employees. The responses of the respondents were recorded in 5 point likert scale. Detailed analysis is as follows.

Table: 1
SA- STRONGLY AGREE, A- AGREE, N- NEUTRAL, D- DISAGREE, SD- STRONGLY DISAGREE

Questions	Classification	Frequency	Percentage
I aware about welfare measures	SA	24	24
	A	39	39
	N	24	24
	D	13	13
	SD	0	0
	Total	100	100
Canteen and Drinking water facilities are good	SA	26	26
	A	21	21
	N	15	15
	D	24	24
	SD	14	14
	Total	100	100
Medical Facilities	SA	20	20
	A	27	27
	N	23	23
	D	12	12
	SD	18	18
	Total	100	100
Toilet Facilities	SA	11	11%
	A	21	21%
	N	27	27%
	D	18	18%
	SD	22	22%
	Total	100	100
Working Environment	SA	16	16
	A	20	20
	N	30	30
	D	21	21
	SD	14	14
	Total	100	100
Overall Satisfaction	SA	39	39
	A	32	32
	N	21	21
	D	8	8
	SD	0	0

	Total	100	100
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PART-3 Hypotheses Testing

H0: There is no significant relationship between overall satisfaction and Medical faculties, canteen facilities, good working environment and toilet facility.

Regression Analysis (Multiple Regressions Analysis)

H0: There is no significant relationship between overall satisfaction and Medical faculties, canteen facilities, good working environment and toilet facility.

Multiple regression analyses are conducted to observe the relationship among overall satisfaction (OS) with MF, CF, WE and TF. The multiple regression models is used to forecast the attitude will be,

$$OS = B_0 + B_1 \times MF + B_2 \times CF + B_3 \times WE + B_4 \times TF$$

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Where, MF: Medical Facility, CF: Canteen Facility, WE: good work environment, TF: Toilet Facilities, and B_0, B_1, B_2, B_3, B_4 are constants.

Results of Linear Regression Analysis

A standard linear regression examination is performed between OS as the needy variable and Welfares of all Perspectives as the Independent variable. When we play out a theory test in measurements, α - esteem decides the essentialness of our outcomes. The α - esteem is a number somewhere in the range of 0 and 1 and deciphered in the accompanying manner: A little α - esteem (commonly $\alpha \leq 0.05$) shows solid proof against the invalid speculation, so we dismiss the invalid theory. The invalid theory for the test is that the two methods are equivalent. Accordingly, a noteworthy outcome implies that the two methods are unequal. On the off chance that single direction ANNOVA reports α - estimation of <0.05 , we dismiss the invalid theory that every one of the information are inspected from populaces with a similar mean. In any case, we can't make sure that one specific gathering will have a mean altogether not quite the same as another gathering

The general consequence of the relapse examination model is decidedly huge (Table 4.25) as (α) <0.05 , i.e not exactly the edge esteem 0.05. This demonstrates ME Perspectives as the free factor emphatically huge influences the needy variable, the OS. The outcome additionally demonstrates that r^2 for ME Perspectives is 0.360 which means the free factor contributes 36% towards the needy variable (OS). The estimation of institutionalized coefficient (β) shows the general significance of this autonomous variable in the Regression investigation. Alluding to Table, for ME perspectives, it is a proof of a positive relationship. The after effect of the institutionalized coefficient (β) uncovers that ME ($\beta=0.151$) is decidedly steady (exceptionally solid relationship) and a significant indicator towards OS as the variable is huge as expressed in the destinations.

A standard linear investigation is performed between OS as the needy variable and CF viewpoints as

the Independent variable. The Pearson connection coefficient ($r=0.50$) is essentially positive relationship, as $\alpha <0.05$ and 25% of the variety in the reliant variable is clarified by the arrangements of free factors ($r^2 = 0.250$). For CF point of view, institutionalized coefficient ($\beta=0.126$) is observed to be emphatically huge add to forecast of OS. The general consequence of the relapse model is huge as (α) is 0.0001, not exactly the edge estimation of 0.05. This shows CF Perspective as the autonomous variable emphatically huge influences the reliant variable, the OS of firm. The outcome additionally demonstrates that $r^2 = 0.250$ for CF Perspectives which means the free factor contributes 25% towards the reliant variable OS. The estimation of institutionalized coefficient (β) likewise demonstrates the general significance of this free factor in the relapse examination. The consequence of the institutionalized coefficient ($\beta=0.126$) uncovers that BSC Finance Perspective is generally a significant indicator towards OS of the firm as the variable is emphatically huge (solid relationship) as expressed in the goals.

A standard linear regression examination is performed between OS as the needy variable and WE Perspective as the Independent variable. The relationship coefficient ($r=0.54$) is fundamentally not the same as zero and 29 % of the variety in the needy variable is clarified by the arrangements of autonomous factors ($r^2 = 0.2916$). For WE Perspective, institutionalized coefficient ($\beta=0.130$) is found to decidedly noteworthy add to expectation of OS (Table 4.25). The general consequence of the relapse model is noteworthy as ($\alpha = 0.0001$), not exactly the limit estimation of 0.05. This demonstrates WE as the autonomous factors decidedly huge influence the needy variable, the OS. The outcome additionally shows that r^2 is 0.2916 for WE Perspectives which means the free factor contributes 29% towards the reliant variable OS. The after effect of the institutionalized coefficient ($\beta=0.130$) uncovers that WE Perspectives is moderately a significant indicator towards OS of the firm as the variable is decidedly critical (extremely solid relationship) as expressed in the destinations.

A standard linear examination is performed between OS as the needy variable and TF as the Independent variable. The relationship coefficient ($r=0.52$) is emphatically noteworthy and 27 % of the variety in the reliant variable is clarified by the arrangements of free factors ($r^2 = 0.2704$). For TF Perspective, institutionalized coefficient ($\beta = 0.131$) is found to altogether add to forecast of OS. The general consequence of the relapse model is emphatically huge as ($\alpha = 0.0003$), not exactly the limit estimation of 0.05. This demonstrates TF Perspective as the free factors emphatically huge (solid relationship) influence the needy variable, the OS of the firm as expressed in the destinations.

Table: 2 Results of Linear Regression Analysis

Variables	r	r ²	β	Std error of estimate	(α) value	Conclusion
Medical Faculties	0.50	0.250	0.126	0.019	0.0001	Significant at (α) <0.05
Canteen Facilities	0.60	0.360	0.151	0.018	0.0002	Significant at (α) <0.05
Toilet Faculties	0.54	0.2916	0.130	0.034	0.0001	Significant at (α) <0.05
Working Environment	0.52	0.2704	0.131	0.022	0.0003	Significant at (α) <0.05

β : Standardized coefficient, α :Threshold value, $\alpha < 0.05$

IX. SUGGESTIONS

Most of the employees are satisfied with the existing welfare schemes provided by the company. The following recommendations will be helpful to the management to improve the awareness as well as to improve the satisfaction level of employees.

- The Management shall arrange more programmes to improve the employee's awareness about the welfare measures working conditions and social security schemes.
- The Management shall consider providing uniforms to all employees. Hence the employees can feel their belongingness towards the organization.
The management shall conduct regular meetings and allow the employees to participate in it. It will help to improve the employee employer relationship.
- A Co-operative society shall be provided for the employees so that they can purchase essential goods at reasonable price.
- The Management can provide better quality and variety of food in the canteen. Also, they shall arrange filtered and chilled water.
- The Company's medical facility is very good. But the Organization may also improve the medical facilities according to employee's needs.

X. CONCLUSIONS

The Survey was conducted from employees and provides some suggestions to improve better welfare measures in the company. The study states that the employee welfare measures are highly satisfactory in their concern which was done through perfect analysis & interpretation. This study would be helpful for the company and also to improve some welfare and safety activities inside the company. The strength of any

organization depends entirely on effective and efficient working of all the employees. The management should take special care to frame certain policies procedures to improve the welfare and safety measures of the organization. The study concluded that the employee welfare measure plays very important role especially in manufacturing company. The management should give importance for welfare measure equal to their objectives. Employee welfare is one of the main tools for achieving goals for the company. So the company should provide maximum facilities which should be beneficial to the employee.

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